
**LEARNERS' SATISFACTION, LEARNING EXPERIENCE, AND DEVELOPING
CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN THE POST-PANDEMIC ERA: AN
INVESTIGATION OF BLENDED LEARNING
OF BSED-SCIENCE PROGRAM WITH
ON-CAMPUS CLASSES
AT GORDON
COLLEGE**

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of blended learning for science majors at Gordon College in the post-pandemic era. It investigates learner satisfaction, learning experiences, and critical thinking skill development through the blended learning approach. The study involves 50 BSEd-Science major students and data were collected through survey questionnaires. The results reveal that most respondents prefer blended learning and express overall satisfaction, appreciating its benefits, especially regarding accessibility and convenience. Blended learning is perceived to support critical thinking skill development by fostering information synthesis and the ability to ask significant questions. Significant relationships were observed between learning experience and age, as well as between learning experience and year level. However, no significant relationships were found for learner satisfaction or critical thinking skill development based on individual profiles. The study concludes that blended learning is a practical educational approach for science majors, providing valuable insights for educational practices and improving learning outcomes.

Keywords: blended learning, learner satisfaction, learning experiences, critical thinking skills, post-pandemic education

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INTRODUCTION

The global COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant disruptions to educational systems worldwide, forcing institutions to adapt to new modes of instruction rapidly. This sudden shift from traditional face-to-face learning to remote and online formats has posed

unprecedented challenges to both educators and students (Hodges et al., 2020; Paguio et al., 2021) and even to the institutions and school administrators (Asio & Bayucca, 2021). As educational institutions gradually transition back to face-to-face learning in the Philippines, exploring effective strategies that can enhance student satisfaction and improve learning outcomes in this post-pandemic era becomes crucial.

The pandemic-induced disruption to the educational landscape has been characterized by widespread school closures and the suspension of in-person classes, implemented to safeguard the health and well-being of students, educators, and the broader community. This event led to the implementation of alternative learning delivery modes in public schools (Asio & Jimenez, 2021). However, this abrupt halt to conventional classroom instruction has created significant gaps in students' educational journeys, raising concerns about the impact on student engagement, academic progress, and overall learning outcomes (UNESCO, 2023). The abrupt transition from face-to-face instruction to remote learning has resulted in significant gaps in students' educational journeys. Studies have shown that school closures and the shift to online learning have posed challenges to student engagement, academic progress, and learning outcomes. For instance, Obispo et al. (2023) tried to explore the impact of computer-assisted instruction among college students during the pandemic period. They found a marked improvement in students' learning outcomes. Another one by Albino et al. (2023) and Asio (2022) examined the screen time exposure of students and its impact on the students. Research conducted by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has highlighted the negative consequences of school closures on students' educational experiences. It revealed that the disruption caused by the pandemic has widened existing inequalities in access to education and disproportionately impacted vulnerable populations (UNESCO, 2023). In the paper of Bautista and colleagues (2024), they explored the emotional state of pre-service teachers prior to their field study during the pandemic period. They found remarkable results for the respondents' emotional status.

As vaccination efforts progress and the situation stabilizes, educational institutions in the Philippines actively explore ways to resume face-to-face learning safely. Gadia and colleagues (2022) and Obispo et al. (2023) shared the learning preferences and the vaccination status of students' results in preparation for the flexible learning modality. The transition back to physical classrooms necessitates a thoughtful approach that prioritizes students' health and educational needs. By incorporating the strengths of both modalities, blended learning offers opportunities for personalized instruction, increased learner engagement, and flexible learning experiences.

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought unprecedented challenges to the education system worldwide, especially in the Philippines. With the sudden shift to online learning, learner's satisfaction and learning experience have been greatly affected. Learner satisfaction, defined as the degree of contentment with one's educational experience, is a crucial component of learner success (Rajabalee & Santally, 2020). The sudden shift to remote learning during the pandemic has raised concerns about the impact on learner satisfaction, particularly in social interaction, course content, and learning support (Baber, 2021). Learning experiences, encompassing the range of experiences a student

encounters during their education, play a critical role in shaping learner outcomes (Mulaudzi, 2023). In the context of the pandemic, the shift to remote learning has created a need for innovative approaches that provide personalized and engaging learning experiences that meet the needs of students (UNESCO, 2023). Asio and Mondejar (2022) once investigated a group of students. They established an association with their science process skills and academic achievement.

In recent years, there has been growing interest in developing critical thinking skills among learners. Critical thinking is a vital skill that enables individuals to analyze information, evaluate arguments, and make informed decisions. Critical thinking skills, the ability to analyze information and make reasoned judgments, are crucial for success in academic and professional settings (Martins, 2024; Facione, 2011). Developing critical thinking skills is particularly important in the current context, where students must navigate complex issues and make informed decisions (Elder & Paul, 1994). Blended learning, a pedagogical approach combining in-person and online components, has emerged as a promising solution to enhance critical thinking skills by providing opportunities for interactive and collaborative learning activities and individualized learning experiences (Bartsch & Weber, 2016).

At Gordon College in Olongapo City, Philippines, a significant change was taking place. The college had adopted a blended learning approach, combining traditional classroom instruction with online resources. Gordon College used a GClamp, a Health Information Sheet, and a flexible schedule to provide a high-quality and effective blended learning approach. Gordon College's approach, combining traditional and digital learning, not only fostered academic excellence but also encouraged students to explore the natural beauty and cultural richness of Olongapo City.

This research aims to investigate the learner's satisfaction, learning experience, and development of critical thinking skills in the BSEd- Science program in a post-pandemic era where blended learning with on-campus classes are implemented considering the various studies within the institution, such as the survey on the willingness on the resumption of F2F classes (Obispo et al., 2022) By examining the experiences and perceptions of both learners and educators, this study will provide valuable insights into the potential benefits, challenges, and best practices associated with blended learning implementation. The focus is on the role of blended learning in developing critical thinking skills among learners within campus classes in Gordon College by providing learners with opportunities for interactive and collaborative learning activities and individualized learning experiences. The study will also investigate the factors that contribute to the success of blended learning in promoting critical thinking skills. It includes factors such as the quality of online learning resources, the degree of interaction between learners and teachers, and the level of individualized feedback provided to learners.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive design with a survey research methodology was employed. Asio (2021) emphasized that a survey involves describing trends in the population by studying a

sample of it. This approach describes and documents the characteristics of a specific population or phenomenon, providing a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences and perceptions regarding blended learning.

Research Respondents

The study was conducted at Gordon College in Olongapo City, Philippines. This setting provided a relevant context for examining the impact of blended learning among science majors within an academic institution that integrates both online and face-to-face instructional methods. The respondents were 50 students from the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)—Science program. These participants were selected based on their active involvement in blended learning courses at the college.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a survey questionnaire to assess four key areas: demographic information, learner satisfaction, learning experiences, and the development of critical thinking skills. The questionnaire comprised both closed-ended questions, using a Likert scale, and open-ended questions to capture detailed insights and personal reflections from the respondents.

The study utilizes a survey questionnaire developed by the researcher with input from a faculty adviser and recommendations from a panel of experts, including educators and instructional designers with expertise in blended learning. To refine the questionnaire's validity and reliability, a pilot study will be conducted among Gordon College students who have experienced blended learning in campus classes post-pandemic. The questionnaire will be finalized and administered to a larger sample of BSEd-Science program students at Gordon College based on pilot study feedback. It includes Likert scale questions to measure learner satisfaction, learning experience, and critical thinking skills development. Cronbach's Alpha values were calculated for each section: 0.88 for learner satisfaction, 0.86 for learning experience, and an impressive 0.95 for critical thinking skills, indicating high internal consistency and reliability in measuring these aspects.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics:

- **Descriptive Statistics:** Frequencies, percentages, and means were calculated to summarize the demographic profiles of the respondents and their responses to the survey questions.
- **Inferential Statistics:** Correlation analysis and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the relationships and differences among the variables, such as the impact of demographic factors on learner satisfaction, learning experiences, and critical thinking skill development.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical standards were strictly followed throughout the study. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, and their consent was obtained to ensure voluntary

participation. The responses were maintained confidentially, and participants were assured that their information would be used solely for research purposes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The researchers analyzed the gathered data to achieve the main objective of the study. The succeeding tables below reveal the findings of the statistical analysis of the study.

Table 1. Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25 years and above	4	8
22-24 years old	18	36
19-21 years old	28	56
Total	50	100

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents according to their age. The interpretation of the age distribution of the 50 respondents in the questionnaire reveals that most students fall within the age range of 19 to 21 years, constituting 56% of the sample. It indicates a higher representation of younger students in the study. In contrast, students aged between 22 and 24 represent 36% of the respondents, showing a smaller proportion of students in this age bracket. Lastly, students aged between 25 and above constitute 8% of the respondents, reflecting a relatively small presence of older students in the sample. The results suggest that the study primarily captures the views and perspectives of a younger student population in the context of blended learning effectiveness for science majors at Gordon College.

Table 2. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	23	46
Male	27	54
Total	50	100

In Table 2, the distribution of survey or research respondents based on their gender is presented. The total number of respondents in the study was 50. Among these respondents, 46% were female, which amounts to 23 female participants. It means that nearly half of the participants in the study identified as female. On the other hand, 54% of the respondents were male, totaling 27 male participants. This information highlights the gender distribution within the research sample. It is a crucial aspect to consider when analyzing and interpreting the results, especially in cases where gender-related factors play a significant role in the study's objectives or outcomes. The data demonstrates the gender composition of the respondents, making it an important component of the study's findings.

Table 3. Year Level of the Respondents

Year Level	Frequency	Percentage
4 th year	16	32
3 rd year	18	36
2 nd year	16	32
Total	50	100

Table 3 presents the distribution of respondents according to their year levels. The data indicates that most participants, accounting for 36% of the sample, are in their third year. In comparison, the fourth-year level represents another 32%. Likewise, 32% of the respondents are in their second year. This distribution suggests a relatively balanced representation of students across these three-year levels in the study, indicating that the research encompasses a diverse cross-section of students from different academic years.

Table 4: Learning Preference of the Respondents

Learning Preference	Frequency	Percentage
Blended Learning	47	94
Pure Online Learning	3	6
Total	50	100

Table 4 presents the distribution of the respondents when grouped according to their learning preferences. The learning preference distribution among the 50 respondents highlights a significant inclination towards blended learning, with 94 percent of participants (47 respondents) favoring this approach. In contrast, only 6 percent of respondents (3 participants) preferred pure online learning. The overwhelming majority's preference for blended learning suggests a positive reception and endorsement of this pedagogical approach among science majors at Gordon College.

In Table 5, it shows the results of the questionnaire on learners' satisfaction. The respondents used a descriptive rating scale from "Highly satisfied " to "Highly dissatisfied," and the weighted mean is equal to 3.15, which corresponds to "Satisfied." As shown in the table, respondents deemed their appreciation for the blended learning modality as most significant, rating it at 3.28, signifying a "Highly satisfied" level, among other factors. According to Terra (2019), blended learning is a modality for advancement as it saves time and money, provides a better learning environment, has a greater reach, and is always customizable. Askar et al., (2008) claimed that learner satisfaction on online courses depends on several factors. Since blended learning combines traditional and online environments, the instrument reflects all the aspects of it. Learner satisfaction on blended learning. Also, as stated by Cheng et al. (2023), a blended learning system is built from the three dimensions of students, teachers, and curriculum, offering a theoretical foundation and point of reference for the ongoing reform of blended learning

in higher education. It is significant in optimizing teaching quality and deepening the reform of blended learning.

Table 5. Learning Satisfaction of the Respondents

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1) I am satisfied with the interface of the online application used in learning, and the commands and controls are user-friendly.	3.06	Satisfied
2) I am satisfied with the laboratory activities during face-to-face and online classes.	3.12	Satisfied
3) I am satisfied with the given learning tasks/assignments during asynchronous sessions.	3.16	Satisfied
4) I am satisfied with the schedule during blended learning.	3.04	Satisfied
5) I am satisfied with the way of submitting lab activities and learning tasks (GClamp, email, messenger, etc.).	3.18	Satisfied
6) The PowerPoint presentation of the instructors and the other learning materials is accessible.	3.22	Satisfied
7) I am satisfied with the discussion by the instructors during blended learning.	3.16	Satisfied
8) As a learner, I appreciate the blended learning modality.	3.28	Highly Satisfied
Overall Mean	3.15	Satisfied

Table 6. Learning Experience of the Respondents

Learning Experience	Mean	Interpretation
1) The amount of time for synchronous and face-to-face sessions is adequate and manageable	3.1	Agree
2) The learning of learners get from e-learning is greater than when it is blended.	2.72	Agree
3) The blended learning modality is learner-centered	3.12	Agree
4) The tests and examinations are appropriate and adequate in blended learning	3.24	Agree
5) Online interactions such as asking questions, initiating discussions, and expressing opinions with the instructor are adequate as well as in blended learning	3.18	Agree
6) The teaching strategies used by the instructors in blended learning are appropriate to the science course contents and aligned with their learning competencies	3.16	Agree
7) The GC health check is accessible and convenience	3.36	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.13	Agree

In Table 6, the results of the questionnaire on learners' experience are presented. During the blended learning approach at Gordon College, students had access to the GClamp website for schedules and academic information. They adhered to a health check protocol before entering campus. The learning modalities alternated each week, offering diversity

in education. Additionally, virtual experiments were introduced as an alternative to traditional lab work, enhancing the overall learning experience for the students. The respondents used a descriptive rating scale from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree," and the weighted mean is equal to 3.13, which signifies "agree." As shown in the table, the most significant factor that the learners appreciated about Gordon College is its accessibility and convenience, with a weight of 3.36, falling into the "strongly agree" category, among others. On the other hand, the factor considered less relevant to them is that learners' satisfaction from e-learning is more significant than when blended, averaging 2.72, which also indicates "agree." According to Banger and Banger (2022), blended learning can help improve communication and ensure that students who are behind receive the extra help they need, while those who are ahead can take on enrichment opportunities to keep them challenged and engaged.

Table 7. Developing Critical Thinking Skills of the Respondents

Developing Critical Thinking Skills	Mean	Interpretation
1) The development of critical thinking is facilitated by blended learning, which allows for the use of various types of reasoning (inductive, deductive, etc.) as appropriate to the situation.	3.14	Agree
2) Blended learning plays a crucial role in the development of critical thinking by enabling the analysis of how parts of a whole interact with each other to produce overall outcomes in complex systems.	3.22	Agree
3) The effective development of critical thinking is achieved through blended learning, which enables the analysis and evaluation of evidence, arguments, claims, and beliefs.	3.14	Agree
4) Critical thinking is fostered by blended learning as it facilitates the analysis and evaluation of major alternative points of view.	3.22	Agree
5) Blended learning supports the development of critical thinking by fostering the synthesis of information and the making of connections between different pieces of information and arguments.	3.28	Strongly Agree
6) The development of critical thinking is supported by blended learning, which enables the interpretation of information and the drawing of conclusions based on the best analysis.	3.24	Agree
7) Blended learning encourages critical reflection on learning experiences and processes, contributing to the development of critical thinking.	3.18	Agree
8) The ability to solve different kinds of non-familiar problems in both conventional and innovative ways is enhanced through blended learning, which fosters the development of critical thinking.	3.16	Agree
9) Blended learning helps in the development of critical thinking by assisting learners in identifying and asking significant questions that clarify various points of view and lead to better solutions.	3.28	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.21	Agree

In Table 7, the results of the questionnaire on developing critical thinking skills are presented. The weighted mean is equal to 3.21, which indicates "agree." As shown in the table, two factors were identified as the most significant contributors to the participants' critical thinking development. First, "Blended learning supports the development of critical thinking by fostering the synthesis of information and the making of connections between different pieces of information and arguments." Second, "Blended learning helps in the development of critical thinking by assisting learners in identifying and asking significant questions that clarify various points of view and lead to better solutions." Both factors have a mean of 3.28 and fall into the "strongly agree" category interchangeably.

Table 8. Differences in the Learners' Satisfaction, Learning Experience, and Developing Critical Thinking Skills when Grouped According to Age

	Age Group	N	Mean Rank	H-Value	p-value	Remarks
Learner's Satisfaction	19 – 21	28	28.84	3.745	0.154	Not Significant
	22 – 24	18	22.14			
	> 25	4	17.25			
Learning Experience	19 – 21	28	30.04	6.571*	0.037	Significant
	22 – 24	18	20.56			
	> 25	4	16			
Developing Critical Thinking Skills	19 – 21	28	29.73	5.482	0.065	Not Significant
	22 – 24	18	19.89			
	> 25	4	21.13			

Note: * $p < .05$

Table 8 displays the differences in learners' satisfaction, learning experience, and the development of critical thinking skills when grouped according to age. For learner satisfaction, the Kruskal-Wallis test showed an H-value of 3.745 and a p-value of 0.154, indicating no significant difference in satisfaction levels among the age groups. Regarding learning experience, a significant difference was found among the age groups (H-value = 6.571, $p = 0.037$). Post-hoc tests may be warranted to investigate these differences further. Regarding developing critical thinking skills, the analysis revealed a non-significant difference (H-value = 5.482, $p = 0.065$) between the age groups. Overall, the findings suggest that while there were significant variations in learning experience based on age, satisfaction levels, and critical thinking skill development did not significantly differ across the age groups. Further research may be needed to explore these trends in greater depth.

Table 9. Differences in the Learners' Satisfaction, Learning Experience, and Developing Critical Thinking Skills when Grouped According to Sex

	Sex	N	Mean Rank	U-Value	p-value	Remarks
Learner's Satisfaction	Male	27	25.13	300.5	0.845	Not Significant
	Female	23	25.93			
Learning Experiences	Male	27	25.41	308	0.961	Not Significant
	Female	23	25.61			
Developing Critical Thinking Skills	Male	27	25	297	0.791	Not Significant
	Female	23	26.09			

Table 9 presents the disparities in learners' satisfaction, learning experience, and developing critical thinking skills when categorized according to sex. For learner satisfaction, the Mann-Whitney U test showed a U-value of 300.5 and a p -value of 0.845, indicating no significant difference in satisfaction levels between males and females. Regarding learning experiences, the analysis revealed no significant difference between males and females (U-value = 308, p = 0.961). Similarly, for developing critical thinking skills, the results indicated no significant difference between males and females (U-value = 297, p = 0.791). Finally, the findings suggest no significant disparities in learner satisfaction, learning experiences, and development of critical thinking skills based on sex. Further research may be necessary to explore other factors influencing these educational outcomes.

Table 10 illustrates the variances in learners' satisfaction, learning experience, and the development of critical thinking skills based on year level. Regarding learner satisfaction, the Kruskal-Wallis test indicated a non-significant difference among the year levels, with an R-value of 4.733 and a p -value of 0.094. In terms of learning experience, a significant difference was observed among the year levels (H-value = 7.311, p = 0.026). Post-hoc analyses may be warranted to explore these differences further. Regarding the development of critical thinking skills, a significant difference was found among the year levels (H-value = 8.898, p = 0.012). It suggests significant variations in critical thinking skill development across the different year levels. To sum up, the results indicate that while learner satisfaction did not significantly vary based on the year level, learning experience and developing critical thinking skills showed significant differences.

Table 10. Differences in the Learners' Satisfaction, Learning Experience, and Developing Critical Thinking Skills when Grouped According to Year Level

	Year Level	N	Mean Rank	H-Value	p-value	Remarks
Learner's Satisfaction	Second Year	16	30.03	4.733	0.094	Not Significant
	Third Year	18	27.03			
	Fourth Year	16	19.25			
Learning Experience	Second Year	16	31.66	7.311*	0.026	Significant
	Third Year	18	26.69			
	Fourth Year	16	18			
Developing Critical Thinking Skills	Second Year	16	33.91	8.898*	0.012	Significant
	Third Year	18	23.81			
	Fourth Year	16	19			

Note: * $p < .05$

Table 11. Differences in the Learners' Satisfaction, Learning Experience, and Developing Critical Thinking Skills when Grouped According to Learning Preference

	Learning Preference	N	Mean Rank	U-Value	p-value	Remarks
Learner's Satisfaction	Pure Online Learning	3	19.67	53	0.472	Not Significant
	Blended Learning	47	25.87			
Learning Experiences	Pure Online Learning	3	24.67	68	0.918	Not Significant
	Blended Learning	47	25.55			
Developing Critical Thinking Skills	Pure Online Learning	3	27.67	64	0.789	Not Significant
	Blended Learning	47	25.36			

Table 11 presents the differences in learners' satisfaction, learning experience, and developing critical thinking skills based on learning preference. As for the learner's satisfaction, the Mann-Whitney U test showed a U-value of 53 and a p -value of 0.472, indicating no significant difference in satisfaction levels between Pure Online Learning and Blended Learning. Concerning learning experiences, the analysis revealed no significant difference between Pure Online Learning and Blended Learning (U-value = 68, $p = 0.918$). Likewise, for the development of critical thinking skills, the results indicated that there was no significant difference between Pure Online Learning and Blended Learning (U-value = 64, $p = 0.789$). The findings generally suggest no significant disparities in learner satisfaction, learning experiences, and development of critical thinking skills based on learning preference (Pure Online Learning vs. Blended Learning).

CONCLUSIONS

The study at Gordon College investigated blended learning's effectiveness for science majors, concluding that it is a successful educational method. Most respondents, predominantly younger students with a balanced gender representation, favored blended learning over pure online learning. The study also detailed the college science students' profiles, highlighting their age distribution and gender balance. It found positive outcomes in learner satisfaction, learning experience, and developing critical thinking skills through blended learning. Differences in learning experiences based on age and year level were noted. However, blended learning was perceived positively across various demographics, suggesting consistent benefits regardless of individual profiles.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the study on blended learning effectiveness for science majors at Gordon College, the following research recommendations are proposed:

- 1) Replicate in diverse educational settings: Conduct similar studies in different colleges and universities to verify if findings hold across various institutions.
- 2) Expand sample size and duration: Increase respondents and study duration to enhance data robustness and reduce biases.
- 3) Explore specific aspects: Investigate varied elements of blended learning (e.g., online resources, collaboration, assessments) to optimize educational practices.
- 4) Address older students' needs: Study older science students' experiences to tailor educational approaches accordingly.
- 5) Implement longitudinal studies: Track science majors to assess long-term impacts on academic performance and critical thinking.
- 6) Collaborate with educators: Involve educators and administrators to understand challenges and successes in blended learning implementation.
- 7) Explore other disciplines: Study blended learning's effectiveness across different academic fields for broader insights.
- 8) Establish improvement strategies: Use findings to enhance blended learning approaches at Gordon College continuously.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Further studies on the effectiveness of blended learning for science majors should explore comparative analyses across diverse educational institutions to validate the findings. Additionally, in-depth investigations into specific learning outcomes, such as critical thinking and problem-solving skills, are essential. Longitudinal studies tracking science majors over extended periods provide insights into the sustained impacts of blended learning on academic performance. Discipline-specific research across various science fields could offer tailored insights into effective instructional strategies. Qualitative methods should be employed to delve into student and instructor experiences while assessing the effectiveness of individual components of blended learning that would inform optimal educational practices. Furthermore, studying how blended learning affects underrepresented student groups and considering institutional and educator perspectives would help refine implementation strategies for enhanced educational outcomes.

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